

MODERN APPROACHES TO THE PROBLEM OF READINESS OF CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation. The article considers modern approaches to the problem of children's readiness for school education. The author emphasizes the role of preschool educational institutions, which are the initial level of education and occupy a significant place in the process of preparing children for school, as they are the first step in obtaining knowledge and skills within the educational system. The question of the readiness of the child for school in our country is revealed, in connection with which there is a need to assess the pedagogical skills, skills, a comprehensive assessment of the physical and psychological state of the child to the new school conditions for him. The author considers it necessary to organize a special purposeful work in a preschool institution, which will allow them to be fully formed and prepare the child for education in an educational institution.

Key words: modern approaches, problem, readiness, children, school education.

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A preschool educational institution is the initial level of education and occupies a significant place in the process of preparing children for school, as it is the first step in obtaining knowledge and skills within the educational system.

The question of a child's readiness for school in our country arises with the transition to learning from the age of seven, in connection with which there is a need to assess pedagogical skills, a comprehensive assessment of the physical and psychological state of the child to new school conditions for him. Schooling is one of the most important stages in a child's life. And therefore, one can understand the excitement and concern that both the children themselves and their parents show when the time for enrollment in school approaches.

School education activates all the previous experience of the child, everything that has been formed in him by this time. Different schools have different requirements for the child, for his development. And in order to feel good and confident at school, the child must be psychologically ready to play a new social role - the role of a student. Physical readiness implies a readiness for health and developmental reasons to successfully cope with the pressures of schooling.

The characteristic features of this type of readiness, the researchers include the general development and condition of the body, coordination of movements, the development of fine motor skills of the fingers. Summarizing the work of various scientists on the consideration of the concept, it can be noted that the concept of "readiness for school" has different approaches to understanding, but the researchers are unanimous in their opinion about the complexity, a lot of planning of the subject of study. At the same time, the authors do not consider such qualities as perseverance, endurance, patience, purposefulness. Constructive activity is also

developing, which can be carried out according to various scenarios: according to a model, according to a plan, or according to predetermined conditions.

These facts testify to the significant development of figurative thinking, as the child in drawings, sculptures, design inventions brings his ideas to life. By the age of six, children are able not only to propose a solution to the problem, but to transform the object in accordance with their vision, they can also determine the sequence of interaction of objects, that is, anticipation appears. Verbal-logical thinking is also developing, as evidenced by the improvement of generalizations. "At preschool age, children still do not have ideas about the classes of objects. Children group objects according to features that can change, but the operations of logical addition and multiplication of classes begin to take shape. So, for example, older preschoolers, when grouping objects, can take into account two features: color and shape (material), and so on. At the same time, the game actions and the game space become more complicated. Game activity, in turn, contributes to the development of the child's ability to coordinate their actions in a group to achieve the goals of the game, to resolve conflicts with the help of speech.

In terms of communication with adults, significant changes are also observed, if at an earlier age contact with elders was due to a specific situation, then in the period under review, cognitive becomes the leading motive for communication. At the same time, despite the possible complexity of information and difficulties in understanding it, it arouses interest and is reflected in the thinking and actions of the child: children share their thoughts and impressions with their parents.

As can be seen from the above, children develop in accordance with two trends: in the process of independent activity, interaction with peers (during play, communication) and in the process of contacts with adults, familiarization with the values of society, since the child is sensitive to the comments of the educator or parents, which contributes to effective preparation for school. Speech

development is also closely related to the development of mathematical abilities, therefore teaching mathematics involves a significant expansion of vocabulary and operating with new terms. In the case of an insufficient level of speech development, inability to understand or pronounce some sounds, the child will experience significant learning difficulties, since he will not be able to fully perceive the proposed educational material.

The presence of elementary mathematical concepts, according to researchers, is an important part of preparing for school. Rationally organized teaching of mathematics to children contributes to the overall intellectual development. With the gradual complication of the material, children get the opportunity, in accordance with their level of development, to expand their understanding of the world around them, while adult guidance is extremely important. Consequently, the need for a certain level of intelligence development, as an important and significant prerequisite for psychological readiness for school, was noted by many domestic psychologists and teachers, who believed that the formation of brain structures, the ability to build and understand logical connections, generalize and differentiate the knowledge gained, the development of arbitrary memory is component without which successful learning would be difficult. The child's desire for success, the desire to gain knowledge, the presence of interest in activities as such - all this determines the motivational component of psychological readiness for school, in other words, if a child has a desire to learn, this indicates his readiness in terms of motivation.

Considering the emotional-volitional component of psychological readiness for school, we analyzed the studies of various scientists, as well as the practical experience of psychologists and teachers. Emotional-volitional readiness permeates all aspects of a child's readiness for school, as he will have to work, discipline, the need to control his behavior and emotions, the author calls this set of

components, both internal and external, "voluntary behavior", which can manifest itself, for example, memorizing a poem, refusal to play, help adults.

Thus, it can be argued that the psychological readiness of children for schooling is a combination of the development of all three components: intellectual, motivational, emotional-volitional. The development of each of the three components is an important prerequisite for the success of education, because if even one component is not formed, the child will experience significant difficulties in learning and adapting to new conditions.

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